

**SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS AND ARTISTIC
THINKING IN ANBAR OTIN'S CREATIVE WORK****Karimova Yulduz Bakhtiyorovna****Teacher of Uzbek Language and Literature,
Academic Lyceum of Fergana State University****Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology****E-mail: yulduzk228@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18280084>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 14th January 2026Accepted: 15th January 2026Online: 16th January 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a scholarly and theoretical analysis of the life and creative heritage of Anbar Otin, one of the prominent female representatives of nineteenth-century Uzbek literature. The poetess's socio-philosophical views, enlightenment ideas, Sufi worldview, and her artistic position as a female author are examined in detail. The expression of women's freedom, moral perfection, social justice, and human virtues in Anbar Otin's works is analyzed through poetic language, symbolic imagery, and Sufi terminology. The study is based primarily on the work "Falsafayi Siyohon" and the poetess's poetic legacy, determining their role in the development of Uzbek literature. The results of the research contribute to revealing the artistic, aesthetic, and spiritual significance of Anbar Otin's creativity.

In the second half of the nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth century, the works of female poets occupied a special place in Uzbek literature. Anbar Otin was one of them. In her work "Tarjimayi hol" (Autobiography), the poetess writes:

My father was Farmonquli Margiloniy,

My mother was Ashurbibi Kokoniy.

They were engaged in weaving, more precisely in belt-making. The family lived in extreme poverty:

They were belt-makers and weavers by profession,

Their bread was always made of millet.

It was often said: "A weaver never prospers from a belt,"

And they never had even a second robe.

Poverty and hardship also undermined family unity. Anbar and her brother were raised by a stepfather. Anbar was married off in the city of Kokand to a man named Zohidxoja. In one of her poems, she describes him as a man of labor, and in the "Debocha" she mentions that he had come barefoot and orphaned from Uratepa. They had four children: Mominxoja, Bibikhon, Usmonxoja, and Ominakhon (who died in childhood).

The future poetess studied at the school of Dilshod Otin. Dilshod Barno wrote about her as follows: "Anbaroy is wheat-complexioned, with hyacinth-like hair, deer-like eyes, a moon-like face, and noble manners. Despite being only eight years old, she shows great

interest in studying the ghazals of Hazrat Navoi... I hope that this girl will become a great poetess.”

Anbar Otin created works in Uzbek and Tajik. The influence of Uvaysi is evident in her poetry. She even refers to Uvaysi as her “grandmother” in one of her poems and notes that Uvaysi was her father’s aunt. As the greatest of mentors, she revered Alisher Navoi:

If you seek a master of literature, Anbar Otin,
Always study the teachings of Navoi.

“Risolayi Falsafayi Siyohon” (“The Philosophy of the Blacks”)

In this section, the author explains matters related to “blackness” through her limited human intellect. In essence, black things are not visible in darkness; however, the crooked rotation of fate has enveloped the age in a black tent of darkness. This tent, through its blackness polished over forty years, reveals all forms of blackness within it.

Anyone with sharp perception understands how black fortune, black intention, and black thought move together in the embrace of darkness during a dark night. When black fortune moves in the darkness, the oppressed remain awake, suffering severe hardship and labor in fear and terror.

Many peoples of the South and East, such as Arabs, Persians, Afghans, the peoples of Ceylon, India, and Kashmir, are dark-faced yet pure-hearted. Like noble white-bodied people, they possess well-formed bodies, limbs, hands and feet, speech, sight, intellect, zeal, strength, and thinking.

These dark-skinned people labor under the burning sun, and although they themselves are scorched, they offer the fruits of their labor to others. It is like a cauldron: though black and burned by fire, it cooks food and feeds people.

There are dark people who, despite their dark appearance, are filled with the light of enlightenment within their souls and spread this light to the world through eloquence and precious words. It is like a black lamp: although it is engulfed in black oil and soot, it illuminates the hut with its light.

Among the foremost elements of beauty are blackness itself: the foundation of a beautiful face lies in black eyebrows, black hair, and a black mole.

“Risolayi falsafayi siyohon”

Written in a Sufi-philosophical spirit

Human spiritual perfection

Purification of the self

Comprehension of truth

Attainment of spiritual maturity

Rich in symbolic and metaphorical imagery

“Falsafayi Siyohon” is a work written in a Sufi-philosophical spirit, in which human spiritual perfection, purification of the ego, understanding of truth, and attainment of spiritual maturity occupy a central place. The work is rich in symbolic and metaphorical imagery, and the image of “blackness” represents ignorance, the darkness of the ego, lack of knowledge, and bondage to worldly desires.

In the work, the author depicts the inner struggle within the human soul:

- the conflict between the ego (nafs) and the spirit,
- finding a path from darkness to light through knowledge and enlightenment,
- achieving perfection through virtues such as patience, repentance, contentment, and love.

Anbar Otin also harmonizes the delicate emotional experiences of the female soul and her response to social injustice with a Sufi interpretation. The work emphasizes the spiritual equality of women and men and highlights that women are equally capable of acquiring knowledge and comprehending truth.

In conclusion, “Falsafayi Siyohon” is a philosophical and Sufi work that calls individuals to self-awareness, liberation from the darkness of ignorance, and striving toward enlightenment and divine love..

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